

The Media and Academic Representation of Princess Diana

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The life of Princess Diana cannot be separated from the media nor can it be discussed aside from academic publications and discussions. Anywhere she went, the media would go and publish news of her as a headline. In other words, the image of Princess Diana was affected by the role of the media. This article will examine why the media always reported on Princess Diana excessively and continually, how it created the image of Princess Diana, and how this image had affected her.

It is not a secret that Princess Diana was considered an icon by the public and highlighted by the media. The media continually reported most aspects of her life and this could be understood based on three main reasons: (1) The needs of media to find international news; (2) Princess Diana was a person who was open to the media; and (3) The high demand from the people who wanted to know the latest news about her.

Firstly, it cannot be denied that the media has three important functions: providing information, education and entertainment. When performing its entertainment function, the media is expected to provide fresh news about popular artists, celebrities, sporting and other events, and so on. Obviously, the media has to provide international and local news to keep them in existence. The story of Princess Diana was one of popular world wide interest. Sofoulis (1997: 15) stated that the story of Princess Diana as part of the British Royal Family was like a 'soap opera' and 'melodrama' and people waited for the continuation of the story in the next episodes.

Secondly, Princess Diana was an asset to the media and often a popular choice for news, primary due to her personality, her media-friendly attitude and often showed emotions in her media interviews spontaneously (Davies, 2001). This was seen to be outside the British Royal Family media protocols, which made news items on her very highly saleable.

Lastly, the high demand from consumers had driven reporters to be consistently in pursuit of her. Stories on the Princess could potentially increase their circulation and ratings. Furthermore, the reporters also benefit profitably from their publications or even just photographs. In essence, Princess Diana was consumed by the media when

she was alive. Her death could be interpreted as being cannibalised the public world wide (Gibbs, 1997).

The analysis of media publication from academic point of view sees Princess Diana has an idealised femininity or child-like character. While Princess Diana was alive, the media often concentrated on aspects of her femininity^[1] and her charitable activities which implied integrity and morality (Barcan, 1997). Barcan mentioned that the media and its consumers idealised femininity^[2] in Princess Diana as a young woman who was relatively less educated than the Royal Family but loved children and mixed with famous celebrities. Princess Diana also appeared to be a shy person who wanted to do something for the world. O'Sullivan (1997) described in more detail the incident when Princess Diana touched the hands of an AIDS patient in the London Hospital. Although the risk of infection was small, she was seen as a saint and this reinforced her image as a person who was both good and brave. O'Sullivan also mentioned that the idealised femininity of Princess Diana can also be seen through the representation of her as a wife who supported her husband, a friend of the poor people, and a beautiful, blonde and famous celebrity. This is one of the reasons why her image of femininity is still warm even today.

The media also presented Princess Diana as child-like figure and created her story like the Cinderella story. Hockey (1999) depicted the way the media looked at Diana as an immature, innocent but modern-day mother who rode roller coasters with her children, yet had a life which was like a beautiful fairy tale until it ended with public divorce. Barcan (1997: 41) described her as the lost girl, vulnerable to abuse, but wanted to be the Queen of people's hearts although called herself the 'Prisoner of Wales'. At her funeral, her brother, Earl Spencer, remembered Princess Diana as a vulnerable little girl whose suffering began when she experienced bulimia, nevertheless she was the little girl who always tried to be cheerful.

In the context of the media's representation of Princess Diana as the idealised femininity, there were positive and negative impacts on her. The positive effect was that the people who admired and adored her, could be inspired and could also identify her as the ideal woman who battled the 'fight for freedom' and portrayed her apparent strength as a woman (O'Sullivan, 1997: 47). However, the negative effect of this representation was that people found that it difficult to know what she was really like. As a result, people felt that this representation of her was fictitious and full of manipulations. Sceptics saw Princess Diana as an ambiguous person who lacked the femininity (Sofoulis, 1997).

The infantilisation of Princess Diana by the media, especially after her death, has its pros and cons. The positive effect was that it encouraged people to forgive the mistakes she had made during her life. It led to the image of Princess Diana which seemed always clean and good. However, the sceptics saw her as a person with an unclear status, floating between an image of a child and an adult who had difficulty in making independent decisions. Another negative impact of Princess Diana's infantilisation was the manufacture and commercialisation of 'Princess Diana' doll. Ironically, Princess Diana's life story here has ended as a toy in the hands of children (Hockey, 1999).

In conclusion, it is clear that Princess Diana had open-door relationship with the media while being presented as the idealised femininity and a child-like princess. This essay has shown that the media also played a significant role in the creation of Princess Diana images. The different portrayals of Princess Diana created a situation like a double-edged sword. Nevertheless, she stimulated discussions in humanity, gender and popular culture.

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[1] Femininity is 'a term which describes the construction of "femaleness" by society and which connotes sexual attractiveness to men' (Humm, 1989: 73).

[2] Idealised femininity can be marked as 'selflessness, fragility and dependence on a husband or father' (Walby, 1990: 105). Similarly, Marshall (1996: 179) describes idealised femininity as 'passivity, dependence and weakness'.